

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE CREDIT-MODULAR SYSTEM IN THE PREPARATION OF FUTURE FINE ARTS TEACHERS

Khayrov Rasim Zolimkhon corners

Doctor of Philosophy of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor

Gulistan State Pedagogical Institute, E-mail: xayrov@mail.ru

Abstract: The article analyzes the activities of scientists-teachers on this issue and shows its scientific significance. The necessity of using the credit-modular system in the process of higher education in the structure of professional and methodological training of future teachers of fine arts is scientifically substantiated.

Key words: credit-module system, professionalism, visual activity, student, independent work, method.

BO‘LAJAK TASVIRIY SAN’AT O‘QITUVCHILARINI TAYYORLASHDA KREDIT-MODUL TIZIMINING AHAMIYATI.

Хайров Расим Золимхон о‘г‘ли

Pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa fanlari doktori, dotsent,
Guliston davlat pedagogika instituti

E-mail: xayrov@mail.ru

Annotatsiya: Maqolada pedagog olimlarning ushbu muammo bo‘yicha faoliyati tahlil qilingan va ilmiy ahamiyati ko‘rsatilgan. Bo‘lajak tasviriy san‘at o‘qituvchilarining kasbiy-metodik tayyorgarlik strukturasida oliy ta’lim jarayonida kredit-modul tizimidan foydalanish zaruriyati ilmiy asoslangan.

Kalit so‘zlar: kredit-modul tizimi, kasbiy mahorat, tasviriy faoliyat, talaba, mustaqil ish, metod.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ КРЕДИТНО-МОДУЛЬНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ПРИ ПОДГОТОВКЕ БУДУЩИХ ПРЕПОДАВАТЕЛЕЙ ИЗОБРАЗИТЕЛЬНОГО ИСКУССТВА

Хайров Расим Золимхон углы

Доктор философии педагогических наук, доцент

Гулистанского государственного педагогического института

E-mail: xayrov@mail.ru

Аннотация: В статье анализируется деятельность ученых-педагогов по данной проблеме и показывается ее научная значимость. Научно обоснована необходимость использования кредитно-модульной системы в процессе высшего образования в структуре профессионально-методической подготовки будущих преподавателей изобразительного искусства.

Ключевые слова: кредитно-модульная система, профессионализм, изобразительной деятельностью, студент, самостоятельная работа, метод.

INTRODUCTION:

Currently, Uzbekistan is taking a number of measures to develop the higher education system in the country. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 No. PF-5847 “On approval of Concepts for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030.” The decree notes the creation in the country of at least 10 higher educational institutions in the list occupying the first 1000 places in the ranking of internationally

recognized organizations (Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings, Times Higher Education or Academic Ranking of World Universities), and, in connection with this, it is planned transition to a credit-modular system [1, p. 2].

The purpose of this work was to study the significance of the introduction and use of the credit-module system in the education of future fine arts teachers.

Literature review: The relevance of the problem of mastering methods of independent cognitive activity by future teachers of fine arts is due to the fact that during the period of study at a university the foundations of professionalism are laid and the skills of independent professional activity are formed. Therefore, it is especially important that the future teacher of fine arts, mastering knowledge and methods of acquiring it, realizes that independent work is designed to complete the tasks of all other types of visual activity. In our republic, artist-teachers R. Khasanov, N. Abdullaev, B. Oripov, B. Boymetov, S. Bulatov, N. Tolipov, H. Egamov, S. Abdirasilova and A. Sulaymanov [6, p. 25] in their works addressed the issues of developing the skills of independent educational visual activity. Their works provide definitions of the concepts “independent work”, “independent artistic activity”, and emphasize the fundamental possibility of improving the quality of education through the use of independent work in the educational process of fine arts [4, p. 1276].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The main objectives of the credit-modular system are:

- organization of the educational process on a modular basis;
- determination of the cost of one subject, course (credit);
- assessment of students' knowledge based on rating points;
- allow students to create their own study plans individually;
- increase the share of independent learning in the educational process;
- convenience of educational programs and the possibility of changing them based on the demand for specialists in the labor market [3, 4, 5].

As we see, increasing the share of independent learning in the educational process in the field of fine arts is one of the main tasks of the credit-module system.

For a future fine arts teacher, the credit-modular education system consists of the following forms of the educational process:

- classroom lessons - lectures on the history of fine arts, methods of teaching fine arts, theoretical ones on drawing, painting, composition, practical, seminar, studio classes, plein air;
- extracurricular activities - work in the scientific library, independent work, individual counseling, assignments, course work, sketches, student participation in drawing, painting and graphics competitions, etc. [3, p. 804].

RESULTS:

The importance of the credit-module system in improving the quality of education of future fine arts teachers is undoubtedly high. The introduction of a credit-module system in higher education in the field of training future teachers of fine arts will improve the quality of education, ensure transparency, eradicate flaws, identify the true knowledge of the student and create the basis for independent learning and work of the student. Today, the European Credit System has been implemented in almost all higher education institutions on this continent.

DISCUSSION:

What does a credit-modular system mean? The credit-modular system, which is a process of organizing education, is a set of modular teaching technologies and an assessment model based on credit measurement. Its implementation as a whole is a multifaceted and complex systemic process. The credit-module principle attaches importance to two main issues: ensuring independent work of students and rating assessment of students' knowledge [5, 7].

CONCLUSIONS:

The introduction of a credit-module system is an important factor in the collaboration between teacher and student. In modular training, the teacher organizes, controls, advises, and checks the student's learning process. And the student independently moves towards the object at which he is directed. Thus, in the conditions of a credit-module system of educational organization, the role of the teacher and student changes radically; from a transmitter of ready-made knowledge, the teacher becomes a consultant, coordinator, and the student moves from passive perception to an active search for information. In the education system, the credit-module system remains a priority and self-education is its main link. To further improve it, it is necessary to develop mechanisms, methods and means of self-education and introduce them into the credit system, using a person-oriented approach.

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